

KOREA INFORMATION -CULTURE AND THE ARTS

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Abstract: Since the earliest settlements during prehistoric times, the people of Korea have developed a unique culture based on their outstanding artistic sensibility. The geographical conditions of the peninsula provided Koreans with opportunities to receive both continental and maritime cultures and ample resources, thereby forming original cultures of interest to and value for the rest of humanity, both then and now. Korea’s vibrant cultural legacy, comprising music, art, literature, dance, architecture, clothing, and cuisine, offers a delightful combination of tradition and modernity.

Keywords: dance, art, comprising music, literature, legacy, culture, tradition, Silla, Korean.

INTRODUCTION

UNESCO HERITAGE IN KOREA

Korea’s vibrant cultural legacy, comprising music, art, literature, dance, architecture, clothing, and cuisine, offers a delightful combination of tradition and modernity. South Korea preserves a wealth of priceless cultural heritage, the majority of which have been inscribed on UNESCO’s World Heritage List to be protected for future generations.

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THE MAIN PART

Gyeongju Historic Areas

Gyeongju was the capital of Silla for about one millennium. The city still contains a wealth of archaeological remains from the kingdom, and hence is often dubbed as “a museum without walls or roof.” The photo shows a scene of the Silla mound tombs located in the city

At the present time, Korean arts and culture are attracting many enthusiasts around the world. Korea’s cultural and artistic achievements through the ages are now leading many of its young talents to the world’s most prestigious music and dance competitions, while its literary works are being translated into many different languages for global readers. Recently, Korean Dansaekhwa (monochrome paintings) have become the talk of the global art world.

The world’s craze for K-pop reached its zenith in August 2020, when the South Korean boy band BTS achieved its first No. 1 on the Billboard Hot 100 songs chart with its first all-English-language single entitled “Dynamite.” BTS has become the first all-South Korean act to top the Billboard Hot 100, as well as the first one in Asia since 1963. This outcome reflects the popularity of K-pop throughout the world, including the United States, South America, and Europe, as well as Japan, China, and Southeast Asia, rather than just a feat of a specific group. It is in the same context that music videos of K-pop stars such as BLACKPINK, a South Korean girl group, have recorded explosive views on YouTube and become more popularized.

As such, the artistic excellence of globally recognized Korean culture was not built overnight. The original artistic sensibility reflected in the diverse artifacts and tomb murals of the Three Kingdoms Period became richer and more profound as Korea progressed through the periods of Unified Silla (676–935), Goryeo (918– 1392), and Joseon (1392–1910). In addition, the DNA of this artistic sensibility has been handed down through the generations to today’s Korean people.

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South Korea preserves a wealth of priceless cultural heritage, the majority of which have been inscribed on UNESCO’s World Heritage List to be protected for future generations. As of 2020, a total of 50 South Korean heritage items are listed either as World Heritage Sites or Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity, or included in the UNESCO’s Memory of the World Register.

Seokguram Grotto and Bulguksa Temple

Seokguram, located on the middle slope of Tohamsan Mountain in Gyeongju, Gyeongsangbuk-do, is the representative stone temple which was completed in 774 to serve as a dharma hall. This grotto is the product of outstanding architectural techniques. It is placed in such a way that the first rays of the sun rising over the East Sea would strike the forehead of the seated Buddha statue in the rotunda.

Completed the same year as Seokguram Grotto, Bulguksa Temple consists of exquisite prayer halls and various monuments, including two stone pagodas, Dabotap Pagoda and Seokgatap Pagoda, standing in the front courtyard of the temple’s main prayer hall called Daeungjeon. The two pagodas are widely regarded as the finest extant Silla pagodas: the former is admired for its elaborately carved details, the latter for its delightfully simple structure.

CONCLUSION.

The Printing Woodblocks of the Tripitaka Koreana, which was made during the Goryeo period (918–1392), are housed in the Janggyeong Panjeon complex specially made for that purpose in 1488 at Haeinsa Temple. As the oldest remaining buildings at the temple, the Tripitaka depositories are marked by the uniquely scientific and highly effective method of controlling ventilation and moisture to ensure the safe storage of the age-old woodblocks. The buildings were built side by side at the highest point (about 700 m above sea level) in the precincts of Haeinsa Temple, which is located on the mid-slope of Gayasan Mountain.

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